

ON THE MOVING BOUNDARY METHOD FOR THE DETERMINATION OF CATAPHORESIS OF COLLOIDS.

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A colloid may be looked upon as a solution of mixed electrolytes so that the relation of Kohlrausch and Weber is applicable in the measurement of cataphoresis by the method of moving boundaries. It has been shown in the following that under proper conditions the results of the moving boundary method are reproducible within two per cent and that the results obtained with boundary method and with microscopic method are identical within the limit of experimental errors.

Three methods are available for measuring cataphoretic speed of colloids namely, (i) the moving boundary method, (ii) the microscopic method and (iii) the titration method.

The first one has a more general applicability. There are, however, some difficulties which seem to have set a limit to the wide acceptance of the moving boundary method. Some of these difficulties have been overcome in the method developed by Mukherjee and co-workers, which lies on a recognition of the conditions at the boundary based on the Kohlrausch-Weber theory of ionic migration (*Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1923, A 103, 102; *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 5, 593; *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1932, 86, 593; *Kolloid Z.*, 1933, 83, 257; cf. also Freundlich and Zeh, *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1925, 113, 84; Kruyt and Willigen, *Kolloid Z.*, 1928, 44, 11; Hacker, *Koll.-Chem. Beih.*, 1935, 41, 147).

In the boundary method the colloidal solution comes in contact with a foreign electrolyte which may influence the mobility of the particles in several ways. In order to establish the suitability of the boundary method a comparison of the latter with microscopic method will be valuable, since in the microscopic method no foreign electrolyte is added. A comparison of the moving boundary method with other methods has been made by Kruyt and Willigen (*loc. cit.*), Henry and Brittain (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1933, 29, 807) and Komagata (*Tokyo Electro-Tech. Lab. Japan*, 1933, No. 348).

In the present investigation a comparison of the cataphoretic speed of particles of vanadium pentoxide hydrosol by the microscopic and moving boundary methods has been made and a satisfactory agreement has been obtained. In this connection the theory of Kohlrausch and Weber has been developed and verified with certain mixtures of potassium chloride and iodocobaltate.

The theory of Kohlrausch and Weber holds quantitatively for the migration of a boundary between two single electrolytes having a common ion (Sen-Gupta, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 14, 685) and also for mixtures of electrolytes (Hacker, *loc. cit.*). Consider the simple case of a mixed electrolyte containing two binary electrolytes AR and BR having the common ion R. Let C_A , C_B and C_B represent the concentrations and V_A , V_B and V_B the rates of migration of the ions. Let B be the slower moving ion, i.e., $V_A > V_B$. For a boundary between the mixture and AR as shown in Fig. 1, the following relation should be satisfied according to the theory of Kohlrausch and Weber if the composition of the two electrolytes were to remain unchanged during the movement of the boundary between them.

FIG. 1.

where C'_A represents the concentration of A ion in the pure electrolyte AR. If the original concentration of AR and BR in the mixture be different from that demanded by the above equation then a more dilute or more concentrated solution will come out of the original mixture and fill the region $aa'bb'$ so that the above relation is satisfied.

It follows from equation (i), that

(a) if C_A is zero, $C'_A = C_B \frac{V_A (V_B + V_B)}{V_B (V_A + V_B)}$;

(b) if C_B is very small, the two solutions become nearly equiconducting and the velocity of the boundary indicates the velocity of B ions only;

(c) for intermediate values of C_A and C_B , one can obtain V_B directly from the speed of the boundary and the potential gradient in the mixed electrolyte layer, but V_A cannot be directly obtained. This case is illustrated by the following measurements.

Measurement with Mixture of Electrolytes.

For a given value of C'_A , C_A and C_B may have any number of values (*vide* Eqn. i) A 0.02N-potassium chloride was taken as the leading electrolyte and a series of mixtures of potassium chloride and iodoosinate were prepared so as to satisfy equation (i) in every case. The potential gradient in each layer was calculated indirectly from the current strength and the specific conductivity (the diameter of the tube was known from previous measurements, *cf.* Sen-Gupta, *loc. cit.*). The results are given below.

TABLE I.

Ratio of KCl in the mixture and in the leading electrolyte.	(Speed of the boundary) (Pot. grad. in KCl layer)	(Speed of the boundary) (Pot. grad. in the mixture)
0	86.3×10^{-4} cm./sec.	34.9×10^{-4} cm./sec.
0.05	75.7	34.5
0.20	64.2	34.3
0.40	56.0	35.5

With increasing concentrations of KCl in the mixture the restoring force which opposes diffusion becomes relatively weak and the boundary loses its sharpness. It is evident, however, from Table I, that the absolute velocity of the slow-moving indicator ion in a mixed electrolyte can be directly obtained by the method of moving boundaries.

The results of some previous experiments with mixtures of electrolytes from this laboratory (*cf.* Mukherjee, Mitra and Sen-Gupta, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 13, 64, Table XIII) may also be interpreted in the light of this theory. A boundary was formed between a mixture containing 0.009*N*-HCl and 0.005*N*-HPic and a pure 0.01*N*-HCl solution. The two solutions were not initially adjusted so that a new solution came out of the mixed electrolyte. The potential gradient in the new mixture was directly observed and the velocity of picrate ion was obtained from the speed of the boundary and the potential gradient as 34.4 ± 1.2 ; this agrees fairly well with the value of $V_{P_{30}}$, *i.e.*, 35.4 (*cf.* Sen-Gupta, *loc. cit.*).

A colloid may be looked upon from the point of view of the migration of ions in an electric field as a mixture of electrolytes, the colloidal micelle being regarded as a large polyvalent ion. Measurements were next made with a colloidal solution of vanadium pentoxide whose equivalent concentration is sufficiently small as in case (b) above.

EXPERIMENTAL.

A vanadium pentoxide sol of good age, prepared from ammonium vanadate and hydrochloric acid, was taken. The specific conductivity of the sol did not change during the period of measurements. The tube and procedure were the same as used in a previous investigation (Sen-Gupta, *loc. cit.*).

Composition of the Sol.

The sol contained 1.95 g. of V_2O_5 per litre as found by (a) evaporating a given amount of the sol and by (b) titrating a given amount of the dissolved sol potentiometrically with ferrous sulphate. The p_H of the sol was 3.01 as measured with a glass electrode and a quinhydrone electrode. The

hydrogen ion concentration is thus $9.8 \times 10^{-4}N$. The sol was, however, found to react with quinhydrone and the observed p_a changed with time. The chlorine ion concentration was measured with Ag-AgCl electrode (Noyes and Ellis, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1917, **39**, 2534) and found to be $9.9 \times 10^{-4}N$ assuming the activity to be equal to the concentration. The sol thus contains about $9.8 \times 10^{-4}N$ -hydrochloric acid, whose specific conductivity at 35° is 49.5×10^{-5} mho. The specific conductivity of the sol was measured and found to be 50.08×10^{-5} mho. Hence the contribution of the colloid micelles to the conductivity of the sol is nearly 1%. The specific conductivity of the ultrafiltrate obtained with cellophane membrane is 48.18×10^{-5} mho, the chlorine ion concentration being $9.6 \times 10^{-4}N$; the conductivity of the sol is thus almost entirely due to that of the intermicellar electrolytes, namely H^+ ion and Cl^- ion.

Choice of Leading Electrolyte.

According to equation (i), an equiconducting hydrochloric acid solution should be suitable as the leading electrolyte. Measurements have been carried out with different concentrations of hydrochloric acid. The falling boundaries were somewhat diffuse. This is to be expected. Only rising boundaries were taken. In columns 3 and 4 of Table II are given the potential gradients in the leading electrolyte E_1 , and the original sol layer E_0 respectively. The fifth column gives the average potential gradients E_2 , behind the moving boundary. The average potential gradient is obtained from the relation,

$$E_2 = E_1 + \frac{dE}{dx} \quad \dots (ii)$$

where dE/dx is the rate of increase of the potential with the progress of the boundary as measured between two side-limbs enclosing the boundary (*cf.* Mukherjee, Mitra and Bhattacharya, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1935, **12**, 177).

TABLE II.

Temp. = 35° . Cross section of the tube = 0.333 sq. cm.

Sp. conductivity of HCl $\times 10^5$ mho.	Current amp. $\times 10^6$.	E_1 (volt/cm.).	E_0 (volt/cm). Calc.	E_2 (volt/cm.).
35.06	11.2	0.94	0.65	0.82
40.20	11.5	0.86	0.68	0.80
45.63	19.2	1.27	1.16	1.24
50.67	21.8	1.29	1.29	1.29
55.70	22.4	1.20	1.34	1.30
61.01	24.5	1.22	1.47	1.37
67.27	26.0	1.16	1.56	—

The values of E_2 were, however, not very constant. According to the theoretical considerations outlined above, E_2 ought to have been equal to E_1 . The deviation of E_2 from the normal value is to be sought to the mixing process taking place at aa' , the initial position of the boundary (*vide* Fig. 1) so that the final value becomes intermediate between E_1 and E_0 .

The rate of displacement of the boundary was, however, constant within 1% during the period of measurement for all the cases investigated. The results are given in Table III. The cataphoretic velocity has been calculated from the speed of the boundary and the potential gradient in the hydrochloric acid layer.

TABLE III.

Temp. = 35°. Sp. conductivity of the sol = 50.08×10^{-5} mho.

Sp. conductivity of the leading electrolyte $\times 10^5$ mho.	C.V. $\times 10^5$ cm./sec.	C.V. (mean) $\times 10^5$ cm./sec.
35.16	86.7, 86.3, 87.7, 88.7, 88.7	87.6
40.20	87.1, 85.3, 85.5	86.0
45.63	85.6, 84.8, 84.9	85.1
50.67	85.1, 85.3, 84.8, 84.2	84.9
55.70	85.4, 84.6, 84.5	84.8
61.01	85.9, 85.5, 83.7, 85.4	85.1
67.27	84.5, 84.9, 84.9	84.8

It is thus seen that moving boundary method is capable of giving very accurate results under proper conditions. If, however, hydrochloric acid is substituted by a second electrolyte in the leading solution, the theoretical considerations of Kohlrausch and Weber become inapplicable and the results cannot be expected to be accurate. It was actually observed that with a mixture of KCl and HCl equiconducting with the sol, both the potential gradient E_2 and the rate of displacement of the boundary changed continuously during electrolysis.

Similar observations were previously made on Fe_2O_3 sol (*cf.* Mukherjee, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1932, 36, 593). A mixture of HCl and $FeCl_3$ having the same p_H and specific conductivity as that of the sol was found to produce a satisfactory boundary. The sol evidently contained some Fe^{+++} ions besides H^+ and Cl^- and the condition that the sol layer will proceed unchanged is that the leading electrolyte must also contain all the electrolytic ions in a fixed proportion. This was found to be the case.

The Moving Boundary Method and the Microscopic Method.

In the microscopic method the cataphoresis was measured in a flat cell at the room temperature (23-24°). The experimental procedure was the same as that used by Mukherjee, Chaudhury and Bhabak (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 13, 372). Moving boundary measurements were carried at 25° in a thermostat for comparison.

The true velocity in the micro-cataphoretic method was obtained from the formula,

$$C.V. = \frac{2}{3}V_{\frac{1}{6}} + \frac{1}{3}V_{\frac{1}{2}} \quad \dots \text{ (iii)}$$

where $V_{\frac{1}{6}}$ and $V_{\frac{1}{2}}$ represent the cataphoretic velocities at 1/6th and half depth of the cell. Since the breadth of the cell was 1 cm. and the thickness only 0.07 cm., the correction for the finite thickness of the cell as suggested by Komagata (*loc. cit.*) is very small for the present case.

TABLE IV.

 V_2O_5 sol.Sp. conductivity. = 37.0×10^{-3} mho at 25°.

Moving boundary method with equiconducting HCl at 25°.		Microscopic method at 23-24°.
C.V. $\times 10^4$.		C.V. $\times 10^{-4}$.
66.6 cm./sec.	66.3 cm./sec.	66.6 cm./sec.
66.8	66.5	66.3
65.8	66.5	66.7
		67.2
Mean 66.4		Mean 66.7

In the microscopic measurements the temperature inside the cell was somewhat higher due to the heating effect of the current. Taking this fact into account the two methods yield results in entire agreement with each other.

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